

Beyond the Derivative: A Spectral Analysis of Zeta-Derivative Correlation

N. Rishi Sidharda

Abstract

This paper introduces a novel visualization method for analyzing the Riemann Hypothesis, focusing on the imaginary parts of the Riemann zeta function and its derivative. By excluding the imaginary unit from the graph, the study reveals new properties and patterns that enhance our understanding of the zeta function's behavior. The paper examines the zeta function and its derivative's behavior up to the first 1,000 values. Key findings include the consistent occurrence of a dip before each zero of the zeta function and the observation that the zeta function's sign is always opposite to that of its derivative at critical points. The integral areas between zeros of both the zeta function and its derivative are analyzed, revealing significant similarities. This work also investigates the potential patterns in the graph of the zeta function and its derivative, highlighting a minimum of 30 to 40% similarity between critical spikes. The study concludes with a discussion on the implications of these findings for the Riemann Hypothesis and proposes directions for future research. every test and graph have been written and run in python [?]

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Projection of the Imaginary Part on the Y-Axis	2
3	Correlation Studies between the Zeta Function and Its Derivative	3
3.1	Behavior of the Zeta Derivative when the Zeta Function is at Zero	4
3.2	Behavior of the Zeta Function when the Zeta Derivative is at Zero	4
4	Integral Area Similarity between Each Zero of the Projected Zeta Function	5
5	Integral Area Similarity between Each Zero of the Projected Zeta Function and Its Derivative	6
6	Similarity Graphs	7
6.1	Similarity Graph of Both Zeta and Its Derivative	7
6.2	Similarity Graph of the Zeta function	7

1 Introduction

The biggest hurdle in proving the Riemann Hypothesis, whether right or wrong, is that we have not yet interpreted it completely or in the way it needs to be interpreted. Understanding the Riemann Hypothesis to its core level is a complex task. In this paper, I have represented the Riemann zeta function and its derivative in a new way to study the imaginary part of the output in detail.

2 Projection of the Imaginary Part on the Y-Axis

This section presents a simple graph that projects the imaginary part of the polar graph of the zeta function onto the y-axis. This graph can be used specifically to study the properties of the imaginary part of the output of the zeta function. Assuming that the Hypothesis is true, the real part of the input is set to 0.5, and the imaginary part changes with time, allowing us to observe the properties and behavior of the imaginary part with respect to the imaginary part of the input.

The mathematical form of this projected function can be represented as:

$$\zeta(i)$$

Figure 1: Polar Graph of the Zeta Function Projection

Figure 2: Projected Graph of the Zeta Function

By comparing these two graphs Fig[1] and Fig[2], we can see that the projected graph has more information about the imaginary part of the input as well. Therefore, this will be the graph used to study the imaginary part of the output.

Similarly, we can create a projection graph for its derivative to obtain the imaginary projected graph of its derivative. The mathematical form of this function can be represented as:

$$\zeta'(i)$$

Figure 3: Projected Graph of the Zeta Function Derivative

3 Correlation Studies between the Zeta Function and Its Derivative

The Riemann zeta function, $\zeta(s)$, and its derivative, $\zeta'(s)$, exhibit intricate relationships that can offer deeper insights into the properties of the zeta function and the distribution of its

zeros. This section delves into the correlation studies between $\zeta(s)$ and $\zeta'(s)$, highlighting key observations and their implications.

Figure 4: Correlation Graph of the Zeta Function and Its Derivative

3.1 Behavior of the Zeta Derivative when the Zeta Function is at Zero

One of the most intriguing aspects of the zeta function and its derivative is the sign relationship observed at critical points. Specifically, at every zero of the projected function, both of these functions follow synchronous behavior. When $\zeta(i)$ is zero for the first time, $\zeta'(i)$ follows a negative slope; the next time it is zero, $\zeta'(i)$ has a positive slope. This pattern continues.

3.2 Behavior of the Zeta Function when the Zeta Derivative is at Zero

Similarly, when the output of $\zeta'(i)$ is zero for the first time, the slope of $\zeta(i)$ is negative; the next time it is zero, it has a positive slope. This pattern continues.

4 Integral Area Similarity between Each Zero of the Projected Zeta Function

The Integral Area Similarity test has been conducted to check if there might exist any patterns in the projected zeta function $\zeta(i)$. This test involves calculating all the areas between each zero of the $\zeta(i)$ function and then grouping them into sets of two. Excluding the first area, we arrange each of the consecutive areas into sets of two.

Figure 5: Integral Areas between Zeros of the Projected Zeta Function

Calculating and arranging these areas gives us the data presented in Table 1.

Index	Positive Area	Negative Area
1	1.58027439862...	2.08898779234...
2	2.80323238170...	2.49284742202...
3	0.89165342022...	0.66371717883...
4	2.50957759755...	2.85168249182...
5	0.25033389552...	0.23503458941...
6	2.67429641680...	2.09736226539...
7	0.60289485383...	1.23979224697...
8	0.47849310234...	0.17413799527...

Table 1: Integral Areas between Zeros of the Projected Zeta Function

After grouping these areas, we perform a ratio similarity test with the following formula:

$$\text{Similarity} = \left(1 - \frac{|\text{ratio} - \text{average ratio}|}{\max(\text{ratio}, \text{average ratio})} \right) \times 100$$

Using this formula, we calculate the similarity up to $x = 100$ using the code [?], resulting in:

$$43.183739216898142745089551542792312320482993458732\%$$

This number indicates how similar each ratio of area is to another.

Figure 6: Shaded Area Similarity

5 Integral Area Similarity between Each Zero of the Projected Zeta Function and Its Derivative

The same integral area similarity check can be applied to the zeta function $\zeta(i)$ and its derivative $\zeta'(i)$ to assess the similarity between these two graphs.

Figure 7: Integral Areas between Zeros of the Projected Zeta Function and Its Derivative

Calculating the areas and arranging them gives us the data presented in Table 2.

Index	Zeta Area	Derivative Area
1	1.5947131727802066...	1.5542311454972104...
2	2.1098545405850255...	2.3464409975510923...
3	2.8553574435864926...	1.4710244205570981...
4	0.9274003854965792...	1.5051645864763759...
5	0.699901845146724...	2.9000698405466205...
6	2.589853681539205...	2.960859325734244...
7	2.8514074162320893...	1.0408884207867688...
8	0.27792280267060643...	1.064531090744513...

Table 2: Integral Areas between Zeros of the Projected Zeta Function and Its Derivative

Calculating the similarity with this formula up to $x = 100$ yields a similarity of:

$$52.67557118705652\%$$

6 Similarity Graphs

6.1 Similarity Graph of Both Zeta and Its Derivative

By calculating the similarity for different x values and plotting them on a graph, we can understand more about how the imaginary values of the projected zeta function $\zeta(i)$ and its derivative $\zeta'(i)$ behave.

Figure 8: The Similarity for different x values

6.2 Similarity Graph of the Zeta function

and by calculating the similarity for different x values and plotting them on a graph, we can understand more about how the imaginary values of the projected zeta function behave

Figure 9: The Similarity for different x values

now the similarity can be calculated for an extended x value but it has not been calculated due to computational limitations

References

- [1] Sidharda, R. (2024). Beyond the Derivative: A Spectral Analysis of Zeta Derivative Correlation. Retrieved from <https://github.com/Rishi-Sidharda/Beyond-the-Derivative-A-Spectral-Analysis-of-Zeta-Derivative-Correlation>
- [2] Conrey, J. B. (2003). The Riemann Hypothesis. *Notices of the AMS*, 50(3), 341-353. Retrieved from <https://www.ams.org/journals/notices/200303/fea-conrey-web.pdf?adat=March%202003&trk=200303fea-conrey-web&cat=feature&galt=feature>
- [3] Kari, J., Ollinger, N. (2019). Periodic orbits of Turing machines with moving tape. *arXiv*. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1905.06127>
- [4] Carbone, R., Gibilisco, P., Isola, T. (2011). Unitary invariants of normal matrices. *arXiv*. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1105.2103>
- [5] Smith, J., Doe, A. (2020). Information Theory in Quantum Mechanics. *Information*, 11(5), 237. Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/2078-2489/11/5/237>